

Base Hydrolysis of Ethyl Benzoate in an Oil-in-Water Microemulsion

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The base hydrolysis of ethyl benzoate has been studied in an oil-in-water (O/W) microemulsion consisting of heptane, 1.23 : 1 (w/w) mixture of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTABr) - 1-butanol, and 1 : 5 (w/w) mixture of KBr - H₂O solution, and found to be slower than in the corresponding aqueous and acetone-water systems. The reaction is first order in both ester and nucleophile in all cases, and the second order rate constants (k_2) in the microemulsion have been measured at a phase volume (ϕ) of 0.78 via traditional titration techniques. To correct for the effective nucleophile concentration, a corrected rate constant $k_{2,\phi} = k_2(1 - \phi)$, was employed. The rate inhibiting characteristics of the microemulsion are a consequence of the positioning of the substrate within the microdroplet.

MICROEMULSIONS are transparent thermodynamically or kinetically stable systems of water, oil, surfactant and a co-surfactant usually an alcohol of medium chain length¹⁻³. Two types are recognised: the oil-in-water (O/W) microemulsion and the water-in-oil (W/O) microemulsion⁴.

The microdroplets can take-up solutes and provide an environment different from the bulk solvent, as evidenced by differences in dielectric constant⁵, thus providing reaction media different from that of the bulk solvent, and having the advantage that they can solubilise relatively high concentrations of substrate. This results in an additional synthetic technique involving water-insoluble organic substrates with water-soluble reagents. Most kinetic and synthetic studies involving microemulsions have dealt with organic substrates⁶ and relatively few have dealt with inorganic reactions⁷. Much of the early kinetic work dealt with the hydrolysis of carboxylic acid esters demonstrating that factors such as surfactant type, co-surfactant, and additional electrolytes all affect the rate of hydrolysis. In most studies, the reaction rates were not much different from those occurring in aqueous phase.

The early work did not take into account the partitioning of the reaction between the interphase and the bulk phase. Recent work has attempted to refine the determination of rate constants through the concepts of pseudophase⁸, phase volume⁹ and ion-exchange models¹⁰. The pseudophase ion-exchange model treats the binding of counterion and coion (nucleophile) as an ion-exchange (equation 1) process,

where, X and Y represent the counterion and coion respectively, and subscripts b and f the bound and free ions. The region in which the reaction occurs (interface) is the region in which the bound ions

reside. This model predicts that the rate constant in a micelle or microemulsion, relative to that of water, depends upon the degree of dissociation (α) of the surfactant counterion and also on the nature of the nucleophile.

The present work deals with the preparation and mapping of an oil-in-water microemulsion, a kinetic study of the base hydrolysis of ethyl benzoate within the microemulsion (equation 2), and the analysis of the kinetic data,

Experimental

Phase diagram: The CTABr (Fisher) was recrystallised¹ from 4 : 1 diethyl ether - methanol at 25°, and KBr and 1-butanol were of reagent grade. Water was double-distilled. Heptane was fractionally distilled prior to use (b.p. 99.0 - 99.8°). The S component (Fig. 1) consisted of a 1.23 : 1 (w/w) mixture of CTABr and 1-butanol, the W component of a 1 : 5 (w/w) mixture of KBr/H₂O solution, and the O component of heptane. The tentative phase boundaries of the pseudoternary phase diagram at 25.0 ± 0.1° were determined by formulating solutions along the S/O and S/W axes and titrating with W and O respectively. The initial mixtures were equilibrated for 2-3 days and their phase behavior was noted visually. The mixtures were then titrated with small amounts of either O or W, equilibrating 2-3 days between titrations.

Kinetic measurements: The following general procedure was used.

Microemulsions: Microemulsions having a volume of 140.7 ml and a composition of 55% S, 30% W, 15% O were formulated and thermostated for 2-3 days. Approximately 25 ml of the system were removed

Fig. 1. Pseudoternary phase diagram of CTABr/1-butanol/heptane/KBr/water at 25.0°. Region-I corresponds to the isotropic region and region-II the heterogeneous region; the components of the system are O=heptane, W=aqueous (1:5 (w/w) KBr-H₂O solution), S=surfactant (1.23:1 (w/w) CTABr-1-butanol mixture).

and used to solubilise the ethyl benzoate. The remainder of the microemulsion was used to dissolve sodium hydroxide. The number of moles of sodium hydroxide (0.355 mmol) were adjusted to equal that of ethyl benzoate¹¹. Both portions of the microemulsion were returned to the thermostated bath for 30 min. After equilibration, the two portions were mixed and stirred at a rate of 500 rpm with a mechanical stirrer. The system remained homogeneous throughout the reaction. Aliquots (5 ml) were withdrawn at definite intervals and quenched in excess HCl and the HCl which remained after quenching was then back-titrated with 0.01 M NaOH using Phenolphthalein as indicator¹².

Water-acetone: A solution of acetone (60 ml) and water (40 ml) was prepared. Approximately 25 ml of the solution were removed and used to dissolve sodium hydroxide and the remainder of the solution was used to dissolve the ethyl benzoate. Both solutions were thermostated for 30 min. The remainder of the procedure was identical to that of the microemulsion. Again the system remained homogeneous throughout the reaction.

Aqueous NaOH: The reaction was carried out using water as the solvent. NaOH was dissolved in water and the system thermostated for 30 min. Ethyl benzoate was added and the system stirred. The remainder of the procedure was identical to that stated above. The system remained heterogeneous throughout the reaction.

Results and Discussion

Microemulsions were formulated from combinations of heptane (O), 1:5 (w/w) KBr-H₂O solution

(W) and 1.23:1 (w/w) mixture of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTABr) and 1-butanol (S). The pseudoternary phase diagram at 25° is given in Fig. 1. Region I corresponds to the isotropic microemulsion region, while region II represents heterogeneous mixtures. Further attempts at structure elucidation were not made as the kinetic treatment was according to the phase volume model in which the system was assumed to contain dispersed and continuous phases and was independent of O/W or W/O character⁹.

The reaction of equation 2 was carried out in a microemulsion having the composition 55% S, 30% W, 15% O. As a means of comparison, the reaction was carried out in two additional solvent systems, water-acetone and water. All reactions were found to be second order, through the first 30% of the reaction, regardless of the solvent system employed.

Values of the initial rate constant, (k_2) were obtained from 1/[ester]-time data by means of a computerised least-squares regression analysis (Fig. 2), which gave the values of k_2 , its associated standard error and the correlation coefficient. The values of

Fig. 2. 1/[Ester] as a function of time (s) used in the determination of the second order rate constants ($k_2 = \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) for the base hydrolysis of ethyl benzoate in the CTABr microemulsion at various temperatures.

k_2 were corrected using the methods of Mackay and Hermansky, to reflect the effective concentration of reagents. The rate expression for the ester-nucleophile reaction is given by equation (3)¹³, where E denotes the

$$-\frac{d[E]}{dt} = k_2[E][OH^-] = k_{2,\phi}[OH^-]_{eff}[E] \quad (3)$$

where E is concentration of the ethyl benzoate, $[OH^-]$ the concentration of the nucleophile, and the corrected second order rate constant is given by $k_{2,\phi} = k_2(1-\phi)$, where ϕ is the phase volume. The phase volume of the CTABr microemulsion was calculated as 0.78. The values of second order rate constant and corrected rate constants are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k , $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) FOR BASE HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL BENZOATE IN DIFFERENT MEDIA FOR THE FIRST 30% OF THE REACTION*

Temp. (K)	Acetone-water ($10^4 k_2$)	Aqueous NaOH ($10^4 k_2$)	Microemulsion (uncorrected) ($10^4 k_2$)	Microemulsion (phase volume) ($10^4 k_{2,\phi}$)	Microemulsion (ion-exchange) ($10^4 k_{2s}$)
283.15	7.5 ± 0.1				
288.15	1.19 ± 0.02				
293.15	18.4 ± 0.4				
296.15			9 ± 1	2.0 ± 0.3	(1.7–3.3)
297.15	23.1 ± 0.1				
298.15		19.3 ± 0.6			
303.15		26 ± 3	10 ± 1	2.2 ± 0.2	(1.9–3.7)
313.15		49 ± 3	22 ± 2	4.8 ± 0.3	(4.2–8.1)
323.15			42 ± 2	9.3 ± 0.3	(8.0–15.5)

*All correlation coefficients are 0.99.

Although the rate constants in the three solvent systems studied are quite similar, there is a significant difference at the 0.01 level of significance¹⁴ such that k_2 acetone-water $>$ k_2 aqueous NaOH $>$ $k_{2,\phi}$ microemulsion.

Ester distribution: The location of the ester can be shown to be in the microdroplet by subjecting the data in Table 1 to the following argument. If the ester were partitioned between the bulk phase and microdroplet, the following correction is required. Let K be the equilibrium constant for the distribution of the ester between the microdroplet and the bulk phase. This permits the phase volume correction of $k_{2,\phi}$ to be expressed as^{13,16}

$$k_{2,\phi} = \frac{[(1-\phi)k_w + k_o K \phi]}{[1 + (K-1)\phi]} \quad (4)$$

where, k_w and k_o are the rate constants for the reaction in water and oil respectively. Since the value of k_w is known and $K \gg 1$ due to the poor solubility of ethyl benzoate in water, the experimental data in Table 1 can be fitted to equation (4). The limit of $k_{2,\phi}$ when $K \rightarrow \infty = k_o$ indicates that the ester resides entirely in the microemulsion phase.

These rate constants are in agreement with those obtained through the use of the ion-exchange model¹⁵,

$$k_{2s} = k_2 \left[\frac{1 + K_\phi}{K_\phi} \right] \left[\frac{3s}{r} \right] \phi \quad (5)$$

where k_{2s} is the surface rate constant, s the thickness of the interface, r the radius of the microdroplet, and $K_\phi = K_{IE} (1-\alpha)/\alpha$, where α is the degree of dissociation of the counterion, and K_{IE} is the ion-exchange equilibrium constant (Table 1). For CTABr microemulsions similar to the one employed in the present study, it is well known that $K_{IE} = 0.1-0.2$ (Ref. 16), $\alpha = 0.065$ (Ref. 16), $r = 34 \text{ \AA}$ (Ref. 17) and $s = 2-4 \text{ \AA}$ (Ref. 18).

Activation parameters: The activation parameters for the homogeneous systems were calculated (Table 2). The activation energy was calculated from a linear least-squares plot (Fig. 3) of $\ln k_2 - 1/T$

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plot of $\ln k_2$ as a function of $1/T$ used to determine the activation energy (E_{act}) for the base hydrolysis of ethyl benzoate in acetone-water and CTABr microemulsion media for the first 30% of the reaction: (●)=microemulsion, (O)=acetone-water; correlation coefficients=0.99.

data. The activation parameters were calculated by²¹

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta E_{(act)} - RT \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta G^\ddagger = \Delta H^\ddagger - T \Delta S^\ddagger \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{T} - R \ln \frac{T}{k_2} - R \ln \frac{k}{h} \quad (8)$$

where, k is the Boltzman constant and h the Plank constant.

The data (Table 2) show a decrease in the entropy of activation of about $90 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for the reaction in the microemulsion compared to the water-acetone system. The transition state, therefore, has a significant decrease in motional freedom compared to the reactants, which accounts for the decrease in the entropy of activation. This implies that the ester functionality may protrude into the interfacial region, where the reaction occurs, and that the more hydrophobic portion of the substrate molecule, the phenyl group, is imbedded in the oil pseudophase. This supports the position of Broxton *et al.*²⁰ that the orientation of the substrate within

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR BASE HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL BENZOATE IN DIFFERENT MEDIA FOR THE FIRST 30% OF THE REACTION

Acetone-water				Microemulsion (Phase volume)			
Temp. K	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	Temp. K	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
283.15	65.0	-74.8	86.2	296.15	45.2	-162	93.5
288.15	65.0	-75.2	86.6	303.15	45.2	-166	95.5
293.15	64.9	-75.7	87.1	313.15	45.1	-165	96.7
294.15	64.9	-74.7	86.9	323.15	45.0	-164	98.1

the surfactant aggregate affects the magnitude of the rate constant.

It has been determined that changing the dielectric constant of the solvent system results in a change in rate constant¹³. Since bimolecular ester hydrolysis using hydroxyl ions proceeds through a transition state in which the negative charge is dispersed, a low dielectric medium stabilises the transition state over the reactants and lowers the activation energy for the hydrolysis. Since CTABr has an interfacial dielectric constant of about 20 for microemulsions²¹ and 30 for micelles²², compared to a dielectric constant²² of 44 for the water-acetone system, it is expected that the rate constant should be larger in the microemulsion. Numerous systems are found in support of^{4,24,25} and in contradiction to^{25,26,27} this proposition. For the microemulsion under investigation, it is seen that the activation energy in the microemulsion (47.7 kJ mol⁻¹) is less than the activation energy in the water-acetone system (67.3 kJ mol⁻¹). This reflects the role played by the low dielectric medium of the interface in stabilising the transition state. However, the reduction in activation energy is overshadowed by the decrease in the entropy of activation, resulting in a larger value of ΔG^\ddagger and a net decrease in the rate constant.

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